

Analyzing the Impact of Social Media, Promotional Efforts and Reference Groups on Consumers Buying Behavior of Eco-Friendly Products in Bangladesh

Afzal Hossain, Meher Neger & Md. Humayun Kabir Chowdhury

Abstract

Eco-friendly products are becoming market leader day by day. As a result, it is raising the demand for the eco-friendly products around the world. Green consumption is the buying and non-buying decisions completed by consumers based minimum partly on ecological criteria. Green marketing integrates a wide range of activities, including product alteration, production process variations, packaging variations, price alterations as well as altering the promotional theme. The paper aims to analyze the impact of social media, promotional efforts and reference groups on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products in Bangladesh. The study adopts the quantitative analysis of three aspects that may impact on consumers' buying behavior. By using convenient and judgmental sampling method, the data has been collected from 200 respondents. Data are analyzed using frequency, mean, standard deviation, correlation analysis and regression analysis. From the outcomes of regression analysis, this study is discovered that all three aspects like social media, promotional efforts and reference groups as the vital facets, which influence consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. The study can help greening development along with influential aspects of the consumers buying behavior. The paper deals genuine way and pertinent recommendations to the greening companies. Eco-friendly products producing companies will be benefited definition all three aspects of consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products in Bangladesh.

Keywords: eco-friendly products, buying behavior, impact of aspects, Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

Green marketing may be defined as the holistic marketing process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the consumers and society requirement in a profitable and organic method (Karna et al., 2001). Green marketing comprises a broader array of organizational actions such as product adjustment, variations to the manufacture procedure, delivery change and more and to satisfy human needs or wants, all activities consist green or environmental marketing. It is designed to create and facilitate a swapping intended so that the fulfillment of these needs and wants will happen with least harmful effect on the nature (Polonsky, 1994). Green marketing have to be maintained production of eco-friendly products without waste instead of getting rid of waste, environmental commitment by re-inventing the concept of eco-friendly product, the price of the eco-friendly products depicting the real cost, create profit by generating the operational occasions that derives from the ecological conscience in the market (Pride & Ferrel, 2008). Ecological sustainability is defined as an environmental marketing approach that involves developing strategies that keep up the environment in balance along with profits for the company. It is a momentous but difficult social target, and many firms are taking at least some actions to save and preserve the environment (Kotler & Armstrong, 2009). Environmental marketing may be recognized environmental stewardship as a business upliftment responsibility and business growth opportunity (Coddington, 1993). An eco-friendly product is referred as naturally produce, bio-degradable non-toxic, non-experimental on creatures, contamination free, nominally packed with natural and permitted constituents (Pavan, 2010; Ottman, 1993). An eco-friendly product is can be stated as eco-friendly, non-toxic recyclable, yielded by organic constituents and substance having a positive effect on the human being. The customer always favors to buy a green product from popular and recognized firms (Suki, 2013). Eco-friendly products are becoming market leader day by day. Consequently, it is raising the demand for the green product around the world (Wahid & Rahbor, 2011). Environmental damage can be reduced by designing, consuming, and labelling eco-friendly products and for consumers awareness is essential to be successive. Eco-friendly products consumers become more careful regarding ambience preservation (Delafrouz et al., 2014). Green consumption is the buying and non-buying decisions completed by consumers, based minimum partly on environmental criteria (Peattie, 1992). Consumers whose buying decision is influenced by ecological concerns will be considered as green consumers (Shrum et al., 1995). Green consumers prefer to purchase eco-friendly products which are more easily recycle and no negative impact in the environment. Targeting those consumers who are different attitude and attribute its culture and social, age and gender (Diamantopoulos, 2003). People are worried about environmental safety, follow green buying decision and consume eco-friendly products are considered as green consumers (Yazdanifard & Yan, 2014). Green consumers are eager to pay premium price because they have knowledge that this additional payment will bring green benefits for themselves and society. Also, eco-friendly products give an impress of being coherent to a progressive environmental regime which prepares us always with positive ecological mind (Florenthal & Arling, 2011). Green awareness escalates the products which are less harmful to the environment, all living creatures, and most prominently, recyclable (Borin et al., 2013). Green consumers are aware regarding ecological adulteration. Thus, they confirm influences of consuming product to environmental pollution and try to keep it at zero level (Tiwari et al., 2011). Eco-friendly products awareness mentions to the ability of consumers to identify the product with green recognition and recall. Eco-friendly products awareness may benefit companies to launch the new eco-friendly product and development sales of existing products (Markwick & Fill, 1997). Eco-friendly products consciousness is vital in guiding the products buying decision. The research has

revealed that promotional activities of products and reference groups deliberately influence consumers' eco-friendly products awareness (Siddique & Hossain, 2018). Green purchase decision of consumers and found that there are numerous consumers who have affirmative and strong decision to buy eco-friendly products but due to high prices and inferior qualities as compared to non-eco-friendly products then do not purchase those (Ali et al., 2011).

The *Broad objective* of this study is to analyze the impact of social media, promotional efforts and reference groups on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products in Bangladesh. There are some *Specific objectives* of this investigation, which are given below:

- a) To show the level of purchase tendency based on demographic characteristics.
- b) To analyze the social media influences on buying behavior of eco-friendly products.
- c) To examine the effect of promotional efforts on buying behavior of eco-friendly products.
- d) To scrutinize the impact of reference groups on buying behavior of eco-friendly products.

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Social media as a vital factor that influence consumers buying behaviors. Consumers steadily examined the blogs on web to see green advertisements. They apply social media to give feedback regarding the eco-friendly products. Social media has transformed the universe of ads and has encouraged a far from outdated promoting. It is harmonized that social media is more useful. Intelligent and more solid than old-fashioned promotion tools (Nufazil A., 2014). Aindrila, B. (2016) exposed that social media is a crucial aspect, which positively influenced buying behavior of eco-friendly products. The beginning concern for the environment, mainly in consumers' products, has clutched the attention of both experts and academics similarly. With the help of new communication tools like social media, the concern for the environment has been broadly communal. So, more and more consumers are bringing to green buying and consume eco-friendly products and services that are not possible to pollute the environment (Zahid et al., 2017). Social media significantly influences consumers' choice behavior, attitude, perception and buying decision-making from pre-buying information gaining period to post-purchase behavior period (Williams & Cothrell, 2000). The role of social media in consumers' decision-making process for complex purchasing those measured by vital brand differences, high consumer involvement and risk, and which are expensive and infrequent. Social media usage influences consumers' fulfillment in the portions of information scrutinize and alternative evaluation, with satisfaction getting amplified as the consumers' moves along the process towards the final purchase behavior and post-purchase evaluation (Voramontri, D. & Klieb, L., xxxx). Mohammadian & Mohammadreza (2012) is confirmed that social media is the vital aspects to influence consumers buying behavior. So, the strong relationship between social media and eco-friendly products buying. Therefore, it is expected that:

H1: Social media significantly influences consumers buying behavior of products.

According to Kotler & Keller (2009) promotion involves sales promotion, advertising, sales force, public relations and direct marketing. Sales promotion is an indispensable column in the marketing communication mix which is a procedure to notify, effect and repeat consumer directly or indirectly about the product and service. Sales promotion is a short-term initiative to attract consumers with the aid of monetary and non-monetary incentives. The promotional strategy is effective where high market similarity survives and it aids in brand switching. Correspondingly, sales promotion influence consumers for stockpiling because offers inspire consumers to purchase appurtenances (Kotler & Keller, 2017). Ginsberg & Bloom (2004) have revealed that advertisement and package provide information like ecological protection,

recyclability etc. affect affirmative intentions to buy behavior of eco-friendly products. Consumers are concerned regarding the promotion of eco-friendly products when consumers consider that it is the conservancy or cause eligible to put down the awareness to purchase behavior (Ann et al., 2012). Sales promotion has become a major tool for marketing and its significance has been enhancing importantly over the years. Sales promotion has significantly influenced buying behavior of the firms' consumers' eco-friendly products (Familmaleki M, et al., 2015). Schlegelmilch et al., (1996) indicated that those firms objective to increase market penetration of the surviving eco-friendly products' offerings must introduce an advertising campaign directed at enhancing concern regarding the ecological quality in the consumers' base. The exploration is exposed that sales promotion is most effective on the consumers purchase behavior. The study also verified that sales promotion and advertising is much more effective in low contribution type products where a simple promotional signal can lead the consumers to purchase behavior a product (Chakraborty, et al., 2013). The study objectives to show the significant effects of the price discounts. The research is discovered that price discounts may change consumers' attitudes and buying behavior regarding a specific brand by moving it from consumers' hold set to consideration set (Lefa, 2009). Green promotional activities as the significant aspects, which influence consumers buying behavior. The study has implications for marketers along with green consumers and generates a good case for familiarize of an era of greening firms (Hossain & Khan, 2018). Therefore, it is expected that:

H2: Promotional efforts significantly influence consumers' buying behavior of products.

The effects of reference group is identified to illuminate attitude-buying decision in biological consumerism using social dilemma theory to find modification between green and non-green buyers (Gupta & Ogden, 2009). Consumers indicate to follow their reference groups' values, norms, attitudes or beliefs and attempt to adopt those on their own as a mentor for buying behavior (Mowen & Minor, 2000). Family members and friends are the vital factors all the way through which consumers became familiar towards buying behavior. Reference groups may influence on consumers buying behavior (Mohammad, 2016). Effect of social reference groups is one of the many subliminal facets that can form a consumer's behavior for products used in public settings. The phenomenon influences favorites for specific brands or products and effects purchase behavior relating to them. All marketer endeavors to tap the subliminal aspects that can aid strengthen the brand associations and drive purchase. The paper finds to assess the effect of three main kinds of reference group effects such as informational effect, utilitarian effect, and value expressive effect on the buying behavior (Reza, S. A. & Valeecha, S., 2013). Marketing and consumers behavior scholars is demonstrated that reference groups' impact consumer choice, particularly for branded products (Ratner & Kahn, 2002). Reference group effect varies according to the group features or its kinds. Difference in reference group influence may be found between males and females, consumers with different educational backgrounds, consumers in different income groups, younger and older people (Park & Lessig, 1977). Reference group has powerful direction on buying behavior, people meet in a social setting and deliberate their experiences with the products that they have used and, precise their likes and dislikes and preference and, features of the product. The individuals correspondingly purchase products or use services which they see others using or buying. Reference group is an individual or group of people that pointedly effects an individual's behavior (Bearde & Etzel, 2011). Therefore, it is expected that:

H3: Reference groups significantly influence consumers buying behavior of products.

Figure-1. Proposed Research Model

3. Research Methodology

The research method which is adapted for the study is quantitative. For collecting data both primary and secondary sources are used. The primary data is gathered from the field through the administration of a structured questionnaire and personal interview. The literature review has been developed from the secondary sources. Structural questions have prepared consists of 19 items for data collections. Demographic variables are consisting of four issues including age, education level, occupation and family monthly income. Fifteen are regarding the impact of social media, promotional efforts and reference groups on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Thus, section 2 is composed of consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products measures by using five point Likert scales (from 1= 'Strongly disagree' to 5= 'Strongly agree'), there is the first question with five propositions which are linked to the social media (facebook, YouTube, twitter, blogs, others), the second question with five propositions which are linked to the promotional efforts (advertising, marketing campaign, sales promotion, coupons & discount, direct marketing), the third question with five propositions which are linked to the reference groups (family, friends, teachers, keynote speakers, motivators), by using five point Likert scales (from 1 = 'Strongly disagree' to 5 = Strongly agree'). Fifth question is consumers buying behavior. Primary data is collected through a personal interview with 200 respondents by applying the convenience and judgmental sampling techniques. Cronbach's Alpha is 0.897 for 15 items of the variable which suggest that the survey instrument is reliable to measure all constructs consistently and free from random error. Data collected from the questionnaire are analyzed by using frequency, mean, standard deviation, correlation analysis, and regression analysis by using SPSS 25.0.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1: Correlation analysis

	1	2	3	4
(1) Social media	1			
(2) Promotional efforts	.584**	1		
(3) Reference groups	.486**	.656**	1	
(4) Buying behavior	.565**	.605**	.643**	1

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The inter-relationships between the four variables are analyzed using Pearson correlation analysis. The average score of the multi-items for a construct is calculated and the score is used in correlation analysis. Lind et al. (2010) stated that the correlations is strong when the value is $r = 0.50$ to 1.0 or $r = -0.50$ to -1.0 . Results in Table 1 exposed that all variables are correlated together at the 0.01 level using the correlation test and the values ranges $r = 0.565$ to $r = 0.643$. Therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem in the study.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics analysis

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Social media	4.041	.905690
Promotional efforts	4.140	.871878
Reference groups	4.322	.790144

Table 2 reveals that majority of respondents have agreed social media (Mean= 4.041 & Std. Deviation= 0.905690) become the most significant aspects in consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Promotional efforts (Mean= 4.140 & Std. Deviation= 0.871878) is another crucial aspects in consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Reference groups (Mean= 4.322 & Std. Deviation= 0.790144) is indispensable aspects in consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Therefore, all aspects are significantly persuaded consumers' buying behavior of eco-friendly products.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.719 ^a	.516	.509	.48740

Table 3 presents that correlation coefficient value (R) is equal to 0.719 which recommends that there is moderate positive relationship between consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products and social media, promotional efforts, reference groups. However, only 51.6% (R-square values of 0.516) variation in consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products are accounted due to independent variable. The adjusted r² is 0.509 suggesting that the three aspects can significantly account for 50.9% variance in the buying behavior of eco-friendly products.

Table 4: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	49.714	3	16.571	69.756	.000 ^b
	Residual	46.562	196	.238		
	Total	96.275	199			

Table 4 reveals that multiple regression analysis is performed to scrutinize the relationship between influential aspects (social media, promotional efforts, and reference groups) with consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Three aspects are proposed and results are computed. The F- value is 69.756 with a significant level 0.000 which is less than 0.01 with 3 and 196 degrees of freedom and it assures model fitness for regression analysis.

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.048	.278		.172	.864
	Social media	.280	.067	.261	4.197	.000
	Promotional efforts	.234	.084	.200	2.785	.006
	Reference groups	.435	.075	.385	5.772	.000

The results of multiple regression analysis in table 5 that social media as the important aspects, which significantly impact on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products ($\beta_1 = 0.261$; t-value = 4.197; $p < 0.05$). H1 is accepted. Therefore, social media aspects are influenced on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Then, promotional efforts as the vital aspects, which notably effect on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products ($\beta_2 = 0.200$; t-value = 2.785; $p < 0.05$). H2 is accepted. Consequently, promotional efforts are persuaded consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Last one, reference groups as the important aspects, which significantly effect on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products ($\beta_3 = 0.385$; t-value = 5.772; $p < 0.05$). H3 is accepted. Thus, reference groups are influenced on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products.

Table 6. The Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Items	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Age	16-30	72	36.0	36.0	36.0
	31-45	102	51.0	51.0	87.0
	46-55	24	12.0	12.0	99.0
	56+	2	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
Educational level	Under Graduate	87	43.5	43.5	43.5
	Graduate	89	44.5	44.5	88.0
	Post-graduate	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
Occupation	Student	160	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Business	15	7.5	7.5	87.5
	Service	25	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
Family Monthly income	Below 15000	50	25.0	25.0	25.0
	15000-30000	90	45.0	45.0	70.0
	30000-45000	30	15.0	15.0	85.0
	45000 +	30	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 presents the different frequency and percentages of the demographic profile of respondents. It appears that respondents are mostly in the age categories 31–45 years old (51.0%). The second highest of respondents are in the age categories 16-30 years (36.1 %). The third highest of respondents are in the age categories 46-55 years (12.0%), and Minority of respondents are in the age categories 66+ years above (1.0%). With regards to educational level, 44.5% of respondents are graduate, 43.5% of respondents are under graduate, and 12.0% of the respondents are post-graduate. Correspondingly about occupation, the majority of respondents are student (80.0%), the second highest of respondents are service (12.5%), and the third highest of the respondents are business (7.5%). Correspondingly It presents that respondents are the majority in the income level 15,000-30,000 (45.0%), the second highest of respondents are income level below 15,000 (50.0%), and minority of respondents are both income level 30,000-45,000 & 50,000 above (30.0%).

5. Conclusion and Implications

A product is called green when its life-cycle ecological effects are lower than those of the benchmark. This way bio-based materials products with recycled content, and hybrid cars are labeled green products even without genuine analysis. Green technology is possible essential theory which plays a role to accomplish the worldwide ecological development. Green or sustainable refers to products that allow for economic growth while conserving for upcoming generations. Green products are those that have less of an effects on environment or are less detrimental to human health than traditional equivalent. Some companies have flourished by marketing products lines as ecologically correct or green. Climate change is the most difficult topic the sphere is facing. Many countries around the world like Bangladesh are becoming endangered and afflicted because of climate change. The demand for eco-friendly jobs is growing all over the world now-a-days to improve the health of common people. Green is the buzz word in all over the world. Green is a widely-used term that can mean a wide diversity of things to different people. Environmental marketing is a current idea that can be applied to end user goods, manufacturing goods and even services. The paper has been undertaken with an objective to discover the impact of social media, promotional efforts and reference groups on consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products in Bangladesh. The study adopts the quantitative analysis of those three aspects that may impact on consumers' buying behavior. The study scrutinizes the three aspects like social media, promotional efforts and reference groups that impact on consumers' buying behavior. From the results of regression analysis, this research is revealed that like social media, promotional efforts and reference groups as the important facets, which impact on consumers buying behavior. The study can aid greening development along with influential aspects of the consumers buying behavior. The paper deals genuine way and pertinent recommendations to the greening firms. Eco-friendly products producing companies will be promoted finding three aspects of consumers buying behavior.

5. Limitation and Further Research

This data may not be the true representative of Bangladeshi all green consumers due to sample size and area. The sample size is only two hundreds. Future research is recommended to improve the significance of the sampling by expanding the sample size and carrying out the survey in different geographical areas. The study is conducted in three aspects only as the independent variable. Thus, there may be some other variables which may influence consumers buying behavior of eco-friendly products. Those three aspects are left for the future research.

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